

QUIZ**LAST NAME: KOVACS****FIRST NAME: PAMELA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. Researchers need to match their overall approach to:**
 - Research purposes, questions, and issues¹**
 - Quantitative or qualitative techniques
 - Sampling techniques
 - Data collection methods
- 2. Choice of a qualitative research approach should be directly tied to the following to achieve methodological congruence:**
 - The research problem and purpose²**
 - The time available to complete the study

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Columbia University: SAGE Publications, 2008), 8.

² Ibid., 7.

- Fieldwork timing and planning
 - Interviewee availability
3. **The process for studying knowledge is called:**
- Methodology³**
 - Ontology
 - Epistemology
 - Axiology
4. **What is an accurate characterization of qualitative research questions?**
- Usually start with “how,” “in what ways,” or “what”⁴**
 - Involve yes or no answers
 - Involve measurement
 - Usually use word like “affect,” “influence,” “cause,” and “amount”
5. **A Literature Review contributes to research by:**
- Identifying what is already known about a research topic/problem and existing consensus⁵**
 - Identifying what should be studied
 - Identifying different research techniques

³ Ibid., 8.

⁴ Ibid., 37.

⁵ Ibid., 18-9.

Identifying populations and sample sizes

6. **Select four purposeful sampling strategies:**

Snowball, criterion, stratified, and convenience⁶

Random, variation, exploratory, and descriptive

Convenience, experimental, criterion, and causal

Causal, snowball, random, and exploratory

7. **Limitations of a research study:**

Expose conditions that may weaken the study⁷

Clarify the boundaries of the study

Narrow the scope of the study

Should not be acknowledged

8. **A social science researcher is ethically responsible for both [insert word choice] and [insert word choice] participants.**

Informing and protecting⁸

Identifying and anonymizing

Labelling and informing

Protecting and testing

⁶ Ibid., 191.

⁷ Ibid., 78-9.

⁸ Ibid., 85.

9. **Identify types of plagiarism:**

- All of the below⁹**
- Using another person's work without proper citation
- Using another person's ideas without proper citation
- Using the exact words of a source without either quotation marks or indentation
- Borrowing all or part of another person's work or having somebody else write your work or parts of your work
- Falsifying data

10. **Trustworthiness in qualitative research considers:**

- Credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability¹⁰**
- Validity, reliability, and testability
- Opportunity, responsibility, applicability, and nuance
- Transferability, replicability, and associability

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie VoIlpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Columbia University: SAGE Publications, 2008.

⁹ Ibid., 24.

¹⁰ Ibid., 85-7.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.